

**22NRM03 “Metrology to support standardisation of hydrogen fuel sampling
for heavy duty hydrogen transport”**

Report A1.1.1

Review to identify the current refuelling protocol specifications and operational parameters that are in place at HD-HRS and questionnaire to investigate the potential evolution of HD-HRS

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Summary

This report discusses the current and future specifications and operations of HD-HRS that may affect hydrogen purity assessment. Key information is also acquired via a questionnaire sent out to several stakeholders where five answers were received and collated. In some respects, stakeholders are agreeing, for example around the vehicles storage, the refuelling flow rates, the refuelling pressures. The stakeholders indicate that compressed gaseous hydrogen has the highest potential for future vehicle storage systems at 350 and 700 bar. However, regarding the expected hydrogen throughput, the stakeholder replies vary significantly. It may be related to the country and maturity of the system. Stakeholders have mixed feelings about subcooled liquid hydrogen probably due to the fact that it is an emerging technology. The lack of supply chain players and the lack of alignment between players including the “chicken and egg” problematic for stations (ability to build quickly and efficiently a network of stations) and vehicles has also been mentioned as a challenge to overcome.

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Table of Contents

1	Introduction.....	5
2	Operational parameters at HD-HRS	5
3	Questionnaire to investigate the potential evolution of HD-HRS.....	6
4	Conclusions.....	11
5	Bibliography.....	11

1 Introduction

Europe aims to be climate neutral by 2050 [1]. To achieve the climate change targets set for 2050 in the European Green Deal [2], realistic technological solutions must be further developed, and this development and subsequent uptake must be facilitated by policies and laws. It is clear that the electricity grid alone cannot support the energy demands of the users. According to the ‘Hydrogen Roadmap Europe’ (FCH JU) [3] in the 2019 report, Europe will potentially be able to generate approximately 2250 terawatt hours (TWh) of electricity from hydrogen in Europe in 2050 which represents roughly a quarter of the EU’s total energy demand’ [3]. Therefore, increasing attention is being paid to the role of hydrogen in the future industry and economy.

Heavy duty- transport is one of the main pillars of the hydrogen industry, which will be used to support the transition to zero emission transport in Europe by 2050. Hydrogen fuel allows vehicles to travel longer distances with less refuelling compared to electric vehicles based on batteries, so it is ideal for fuelling heavy duty- trucks and trailers, and public transit buses [4], which travel hundreds of kilometres at a time. Secondly heavy-duty trucks and trailer, transit buses have known routes which simplify the deployment of refuelling points.

The first hydrogen fuel-cell electric heavy-duty vehicles are already being rolled out in Europe. From the mid-2020s on, the vehicle offering will increase significantly, with at least 60,000 trucks expected to be in operation by 2030. A large infrastructure comprising truck-suitable hydrogen refuelling stations will then soon be required. According to the ACEA (European Automobile Manufacturers Association) [5], an EU-wide target of around 300 truck-suitable hydrogen refuelling stations by 2025, and at least 1000 no later than by 2030, should be set. In 2021, only 16 out of 144 HRS delivering 350 bar H₂ to HDVs, mainly city buses.

This report discusses the current and future specifications and operations of HD-HRS that may affect hydrogen purity assessment. Key information was acquired via a questionnaire sent out to several stakeholders.

2 Operational parameters at HD-HRS

Using the information found in the report “Overview Hydrogen Refuelling for Heavy Duty Vehicles”, Table 1 summarizes the operational parameters of HD-HRS for different supply options:

Table 1. Operational parameters at HD-HRS [6]

Supply option	CGH ₂ , LH ₂	CGH ₂ , LH ₂	LH ₂	LH ₂ (CGH ₂ feasible)
HRS specifications				
Main components	H ₂ storage, compressor or cryo pump, cooling unit (if CGH ₂), dispenser (nozzle, hose)	H ₂ storage, compressor or cryo pump, cooling unit (if CGH ₂), dispenser (nozzle, hose)	H ₂ storage, subcooled liquid H ₂ pump, dispenser (nozzle, hose)	LH ₂ storage, cryo pump, dispenser (nozzle, hose)
H ₂ storage type	Depending on specification	Depending on specification	Depending on specification either:	Depending on specification either:

	either: trailer swap, supply storage, pipeline	either: trailer swap, supply storage, pipeline	trailer swap, supply storage	trailer swap, supply storage
Refuelling pressure	350 bar	700 bar	Approx. 16 bar	300 bar
Ease of expanding to 700 bar passenger vehicles refuelling	Complex and costly integration due to higher compressor ratio and cooling demand	Relatively simple expandability due to existing technology and lower performance requirements	Complex and costly integration of additional high pressure cryo pump system, nozzle, hose etc	Complex and costly integration of additional high pressure cryo pump system, nozzle, hose etc
Data communication between HRS and vehicle	Necessary for better performance	Necessary for better performance	Not required	Not required
Targeted max flow rate	300 g/s	300 g/s	400-500 kg/h (per pump)	200-800 kg/h per pump
Vehicle specifications				
H ₂ tank pressure (MAWP*)	350 (437.5 bar)	700 (875 bar)	Approx. 5-16 bar	200-800 kg/h per pump
VH ₂ tank temperature	-40 to 85 °C	-40 to 85 °C	-248 to -245 °C	Approx. -240 °C to -150 °C
Storage capacity	Today < 42.5 kg (intended > 42.5 kg)	Up to 100 kg	> 80 kg	> 80 kg

*MAWP: Maximum allowable working pressure

Another source of information for the requirements for the filling stations of the future is [7], but the site is only in German. In order to estimate the needs of future hydrogen filling stations, this document use data from today's diesel filling stations. The classification for stations is using symbols for the size, xs, s, m, l and xl. The sizes of hydrogen refuelling stations are independent of the H₂ refuelling forms (CGH₂/CcH₂/sLH₂) and refer to the minimum capacities to be achieved (xs = 0.4 t H₂/d) [7]. In order to determine future demand for hydrogen refuelling stations and to better assess the requirements for the transformation of today's diesel refuelling stations into hydrogen refuelling stations, a hydrogen refuelling station reference tool has been developed and will be soon available on the website [7].

3 Questionnaire to investigate the potential evolution of HD-HRS

A questionnaire has been prepared to investigate the potential evolution of HD-HRS. It contained 10 questions:

- 1) What will be the general requirements for hydrogen supply?
- 2) What will be the future vehicle storage systems?
- 3) Which supply options should be preferred? (CGH₂, sLH₂, CcH₂)

- 4) What will be the main components of the station? (H₂ storage, compressor, cryo pump, cooling unit, dispenser...)
- 5) What will be the HRS H₂ storage type? (trailer swap, supply storage, pipeline..)
- 6) What will be the refuelling pressure? (in bar)
- 7) What will be the targeted max. flow rate? (in g/s)
- 8) What will be the vehicle storage capacity? (in kg)
- 9) What is the biggest challenge that can impair the development of HD-HRS?
- 10) Any other comments?

The questionnaire was sent to several stakeholders and totally, five answers were received.

The responses are collated in the following tables.

1) General requirements

Table 2. Summary of responses on expected hydrogen throughput in kg per day and per year

	Max (kg)	Min (kg)	Average (kg)	Comments
Hydrogen throughput per day in kg	260	180	220	Minimum is set by AFIR in Europe
	4000	800	1800	
	2000	200	1000	
	100000	500	2000-4000	
	8000	1000	4000	
Annual demand	90 000	25000	60000	
	1320000	256000	560000	
	No answer	No answer	No answer	
	No answer	No answer	No answer	
	2000000	200000	No answer	

The stakeholder replies vary significantly. It may be related to the country and maturity of the system. However, it should be noted that the average amount of hydrogen throughput per day ranges from 220 – 4000 kg. It is a significant increase from today situation. The annual demand reaches a minimum of 25 tons per year up to a maximum of 2000 tons. The increase in volume is significant.

2) Future vehicle storage systems

Table 3. summary of responses for future vehicle sotrage systems

Type	Pressure (bar)	Temperature (°C)	High potential	Comments
CGH2 (compressed gaseous hydrogen)	350	15	Yes (five answers)	For buses
CGH2 (compressed gaseous hydrogen)	700	15	Yes (five answers)	
sLH2 (subcooled liquid hydrogen)	16	-247	Yes (three answers), NO (two answers)	
CcH2 (cryo-compressed hydrogen)	300	-219	NO (three answers), no answer from two participants	

The stakeholders indicate that compressed gaseous hydrogen has the highest potential for future vehicle storage systems at 350 and 700 bar. Stakeholders have mixed feelings about subcooled liquid hydrogen probably due to the fact that it is an emerging technology.

3) Preferred supply options

Table 4. summary of responses for the preferred supply options

Reply 1	LH2, CGH2
Reply 2	Supply to station: Preferably LH2, then pipeline and gas trailer Supply at station: CGH2, sLH2, LH2
Reply 3	CGH2 as mainstream, with a possibility of LH2 for long haul.
Reply 4	Start with CGH2 700 bar. Other storage solutions are possible in the future depending on market development
Reply 5	From the supply of the station, LH2 offers the broadest spectrum. About the station delivery itself, it will depend on the location and the need of the end users

The stakeholder responses highlight that compressed gaseous hydrogen is the first step (may become mainstream). They are expecting liquid hydrogen supply to be deployed for the long-haul vehicles.

4) Main components of the station

Table 5. summary of responses for the main components of the station

Reply 1	H2 storage, compressors (variety most likely), dispenser
Reply 2	Depends on what type of station. Gas-to-gas; liquid-to-gas and liquid-to-liquid are all feasible, so gaseous and liquid H2 storage is feasible, as are compressors, cryo pumps, cooling units, vaporisers
Reply 3	Appropriate cooling and appropriate compression are important
Reply 4	Station manufacturer to answer
Reply 5	All are important. Not sure to understand the question very well

The stakeholder responses highlight that compressor and cooling units are critical, but all components of the station need to be considered (no consensus on a main component).

5) HRS H2 storage type

Table 6. summary of responses for HRS hydrogen storage type

Reply 1	Trailers, storage cylinders
Reply 2	Most likely to be trailer swap with some stationary storage. LH2 delivery, with LH2 and gaseous storage to become increasingly prevalent.
Reply 3	Pipeline if available, supply storage in other cases.

Reply 4	We see trailer swap as the solution to be implemented in short/medium term. Longer term all options are possible.
Reply 5	For high demand on the long-term pipeline or LH2 trailer transfer are the most suitable

The stakeholder responses highlight the complexity of storage. The views diverge but trailer swap and storage cylinders which are the current situation, are mentioned several times.

6) Refuelling pressure

Table 7. summary of responses for refuelling pressure.

Reply 1	350 barg (including high flow), 700 barg (potentially including high flow)
Reply 2	No answer
Reply 3	most probably 700 bar for long haul and high power applications, 350 bar for the short distances
Reply 4	For CGH2, up to 950 bar on station
Reply 5	700 bar is set as mandatory in the AFIR

The stakeholder responses highlight that 350 bar (high flow) is expected for the short distance while most responses indicate 700 bar as the most common refuelling pressure including high flow.

7) Targeted max. flow rate

Table 8. summary of responses for targeted maximum flow rate

Reply 1	120 - 300 g/s
Reply 2	No answer
Reply 3	300 g/s
Reply 4	For CGH2 max 300 g/s. (Typical 120-150 g/s)
Reply 5	Theoretically 300 g/s according to current standardization. In the field probably < 200 g/s

The stakeholder responses highlight the targeted maximum flow rate ranging from 120 g/s in the field to 300 g/s. The flow rate is quite higher from the current light-duty flow rate.

8) Vehicle storage capacity

Table 9. summary of responses for vehicle storage capacity

Reply 1	> 25 kg
Reply 2	No answer
Reply 3	70-80 kg at 700 bar, 30-40 kg at 350 bar
Reply 4	Up to 80 kg
Reply 5	Around 60 – 100 kg

The stakeholder responses highlight the vehicle storage capacity being between 30 – 100 kg with the low capacity for the 350-bar pressure.

9) Biggest challenges

Table 10. summary of responses on biggest challenges.

Reply 1	Equipment availability (e.g., newly designed nozzles) Advanced communications development/availability System design not being able to perform well enough at higher flows
Reply 2	Appropriate SLH2 is not really designed to fill warm systems and a minimum fill is required for pressure collapse. What is the expected minimum amount to be delivered and size of tank for sampling? How will a station be informed that it may not be connecting to a normally configured / sized vessel? Can we establish a standard communication structure that tells a station a sampling rather than a refuelling is occurring? Availability of refuelling protocols; Technical Readiness of equipment; Lack of supply chain players; Lack of alignment between players (vehicle OEMS especially), on preferred options
Reply 3	Cost and the chicken-and-egg problem
Reply 4	Availability of standards. Chicken and egg for vehicle and stations. The extreme scale of station and infrastructure network build out necessary for wide introduction of hydrogen trucks.
Reply 5	Ability to build quickly and efficiently a station network

The response highlighted the infrastructure challenge especially getting available equipment (HD designed nozzle). It would slow down the availability of infrastructure (building or maintaining). The availability of standard is another problem in order to deploy quickly the system as new standard may create discrepancies between existing systems and new standard implemented in the future. The cost and supply chain availability are problems that must be solved in order to keep the heavy-duty transport competitive. The chicken and egg problem between development of vehicles and infrastructure is another challenge mentioned several times.

10) Other comments

Table 11. summary of responses for other comments.

Reply 1	Lack of political support for hydrogen in some countries
Reply 2	SLH2 is not really designed to fill warm systems and a minimum fill is required for pressure collapse. What is the expected minimum amount to be delivered and size of tank for sampling? How will a station be informed that it may not be connecting to a normally configured / sized vessel? Can we establish a standard communication structure that tells a station a sampling rather than a refuelling is occurring?
Reply 3	Please be aware of an upcoming refuelling and charging noise regulation from the European Union that may be of interest to your project.
Reply 4	No other comments
Reply 5	Important study made on future HRS: Tankstelle der Zukunft (tankstelle-der-zukunft.de) (only in German) In contains many information, that can help answer the questions

The responses highlighted other concerns related to the lack of political support and incentives, the new upcoming regulation (i.e., noise) or the clarity on how to perform sampling without communication between the HRS and the sampling system.

4 Conclusions

This report discusses the current and future specifications and operations of HD-HRS that may affect hydrogen purity assessment. The current operational parameters of HD-HRS for different supply options are briefly summarized using information found in the report “Overview Hydrogen Refuelling for Heavy Duty Vehicles”.

According to stakeholders who answered a questionnaire to investigate the potential evolution of HD-HRS, many challenges arise before this infrastructure is in place and many efforts are needed including political support. Among others, technical readiness of equipment is often mentioned in particular, the availability of adapted equipment (e.g., newly designed nozzles), the development/availability of advanced communications and systems able to perform well at higher flows, and availability of refuelling protocols.

In some respects, stakeholders are agreeing, for example around the vehicles storage (30 – 100 kg), the refuelling flow rate between 120 – 300 g/s, the refuelling pressure of 350 and 700 bar for long haul. The status is compressed hydrogen gas, but storage as liquid hydrogen is expected in the future. However, regarding the expected hydrogen throughput, the stakeholder replies vary significantly. It may be related to the country and maturity of the system.

The lack of supply chain players and the lack of alignment between players including the “chicken and egg” problematic for stations (ability to build quickly and efficiently a network of stations) and vehicles has also been mentioned as a challenge to overcome.

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